

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: KINDO****FIRST NAME: SOULEYMANE****PROGRAM CODE: DME****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: GULMA****Edit or delete text to show the actual information below:**

The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did did not use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did did not use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: xx%

The author used the following software (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

List your seven critical concepts with the page number in the text (then bold these terms in your RP)(samples below):

1. Introduction
2. Essay writing (EUCLID 2024, 6-12)
3. Punctuations (EUCLID 2024, 15-23)
4. American English vs British English (EUCLID 2024, 24-32)
5. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2024, 33-39)
6. CMS crib sheet (EUCLID 2024, 43-57)
7. Latin abbreviations and expressions (EUCLID 2024, 58-64)

INTERNATIONAL ACADEMIC WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

Writing is an essential tool to master in the academic and professional world. At Euclid University, it serves as a foundational resource covering critical aspects such as essay composition, punctuation, plagiarism avoidance, and adherence to style conventions. It is good to improve your writing skills, as it is an essential tool for research and critical thinking. The document we are studying is on international academic writing. It was written by two eminent professors (Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma) at Euclid University in 2024. It is about understanding the fundamentals of writing academic papers. In its fifth iteration, the period one coursepack delivers essential guidance for both international academics and professionals on the fundamentals of paper writing (EUCLID 2024, 3).

In this period one response paper, I will go through the key concepts about essay writing, punctuations, American English compared to British English, plagiarism, and Latin abbreviations and expressions.

2) **ESSAY WRITING**

Writing an essay can be done on many occasions and in many subject areas. We will discuss essays intended for academic purposes. Examples of academic writing include research findings or reports or empirical fieldwork which may not or may be published in journals, books, newspapers, or other periodicals (or remain as manuscripts, theses, or dissertations); monographs; conference papers; books; or literature review; explication; technical report; translation; students' presentations; as well as undergraduate versions of the above. Writing an essay follows some criteria to have an acceptable paper, both in terms of the content's quality and in the paper's form or style.

Three steps must be undertaken before starting an essay. The first step is an early start-up. The second step is to define the question and analyze the different tasks. The third is to start making a draft for an initial plan.

3) **PUNCTUATIONS**

When writing an academic paper, it is crucial to understand the different rules when using a particular punctuation and distinguish between correct and incorrect punctuation. I will be writing about some commonly used punctuation marks.

i) Full stop, exclamation mark, and question mark

These punctuations are used once and only one time at the end of every sentence. A complete stop cannot be used at the end of titles, even if the title makes a sentence. However, if the title ends with an exclamation mark or question mark, we can include it. It is optional to use a full stop if it is followed or preceded by an ellipsis. A full stop, not an exclamation mark, is recommended at the end of a reported imperative.

ii) Comma

Commas are used in writing to make a listing and join ideas or clauses. Here are some examples of how to use commas when writing a paper. A pair of commas can surround a non-defining clause (one that adds descriptive information but can be removed without losing a sentence's meaning). A comma can also be used after an introductory adverb, adverbial phrase, subordinate clause, or a pair of commas surrounding it if it is in the middle of a sentence. Example: However, it was too late for that. It was, however, too late for that.

We cannot use commas to surround a defining clause (which cannot be removed without losing the meaning of a sentence). Using a comma where defining information is used at the start of a sentence is also impossible. Example: we should not write: His friend, Sam, was his second. Instead, we should note that his friend Sam was his second.

4) AMERICAN VS. BRITISH ENGLISH

American and British English are both variants of World English. American English is currently the dominant influence on “world English” (cf. British English). These two variants of English have some similarities and also some differences in speaking and writing. We will be looking at some of these aspects.

i) Different pronunciation, although exact spelling

In this category of words, we can cite the words like advertisement, controversy, secretary, and renaissance.

ii) Different spelling, although the same pronunciation

Pairs of words like axe/ax, colour/color, centre/center, cheque/check, defence/defense can be found in this category.

iii) Same term, different but similar spelling and pronunciation

We have words like aluminium/aluminum and maths/math in this category.

iv) Punctuation with business (formal) vs. social (informal) letters

In proper British English, we should write like: Dear Mr Smith,

In colloquial British English, we write: Dear Aunt Sally,

In standard American English, we should note: Dear Mr. Smith:

5) PLAGIARISM

In academic writing, one of the most essential things the writer should do is to avoid plagiarism. Plagiarism is when the writer uses a source of information without crediting the author of that source of information (EUCLID 2024, 34), taking someone else’s words or ideas such as quoting, paraphrasing, copying, and pasting from the internet and not giving credit to the author. Having someone write a paper for you, put your name on it, and give it to your professor would be plagiarism.

We should always give credit to the author anytime we use a quote, paraphrase, statistics/data, or visuals that are not our own. Plagiarism is wrong, unethical, and considered a severe offense in the academic world. It is better to provide the source and the author of any information that is not yours and that you will be using for your paper. We have two main ways to do that: in-text citations and the works cited list.

6) **CMS CRIB SHEET**

There are many formatting styles when writing books or research papers. We can cite the CMS, the Turabian style, the Harvard style, the Oxford style... At Euclid University, the CMS and the Turabian styles are the two main styles used when writing papers. Following these two styles, we will give the most crucial point in paper formatting.

i) Spelling

In spelling words, when using the CMS or the Turabian style, it is recommended to use the Webster or the Merriam-Webster dictionary.

ii) Capitalization

We have three types or forms of capitalization: full caps, heading caps, and sentence caps. The full caps formatting capitalizes every character of every word. The heading caps, also called headlines, capitalize the first character of each word. The sentence caps capitalize the first word of a title or heading, the first word after a colon, and proper nouns.

iii) Page format

The Chicago Manual of Style focuses on book publishing and has few instructions for formatting papers. Turabian's Manual for Writers is the official guide to applying the Chicago style to "term papers, theses, and dissertations," that is, final manuscripts (EUCLID 2024, 50).

1. Margins. "The normal page dimensions are 8½ by 11 inches.
2. Fonts. "The eminently readable Times Roman is perhaps the best choice.
3. Indents. The standard indent is one-half inch.
4. Paper. Use only 8½ by 11-inch white paper.
5. Justification. "Right margins should be justified (aligned) only if done without leaving significant gaps between words.
6. Spacing. "The text should be double-spaced except for block quotations, notes, captions, and long headings.
7. Page numbers for each page beginning a significant section of a paper (the first text page, bibliography, notes, appendix) are placed at the bottom center of the page, three-quarters of an inch from the page edge. Page numbers on other pages go in the upper right corner, double-spaced above the text. (Euclid 2024, 50)

7) LATIN ABBREVIATIONS AND EXPRESSIONS

In reading and writing, you will always encounter some kinds of abbreviations. These abbreviations are usually called Latin abbreviations and are meant to simplify some words or expressions. Here are some of the widely used ones in writing. i.e., id est (that is), e.g., exempli gratia (for example)

- a priori: from what comes before
- a posteriori: from what comes after
- in silico: in computer simulation
- cf. confer compare
- pp. pluta paper pages
- p.p. per pro; per procuracionem on behalf of; used when someone signs a letter by authority or proxy because another person is not available
- vs. versus against
- v.v. Vice versa, the other way round

REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. 2024. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Fifth Edition. Washington DC: Euclid University Press.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. *ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1*. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.